
A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION AT WORK PLACE WITH REFERENCE TO BSNL, KADAPA

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Abstract:

Employee motivation at work place is an important area in human resource management that contributes to the performance of the employees. Many organizations are planning new strategies and ways in order to safeguard their employees. Better motivators at work place makes the employees feel satisfied and put more efforts to increase the productivity and profitability of the company. The study analyses the opinion of employees on motivational factors at work place and basing on the response, the statistical tools like factor analysis and chi-square test are applied. The results of the study are very useful to every company which needs to manage its employees and make them satisfied at work place. The study helps in retaining the employees in the company for a long time.

Keywords: Motivation; Performance; Productivity; Rewards; Workplace and Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

The only way to get people to work hard is to motivate them. Today, people must understand why they're working hard. Every individual in an organization is motivated by some different way. When talking in term of employee motivation, it can be simply defined as "a reflection of the level of energy, commitment, and creativity that a company's workers bring to their jobs." The job of a manager in the workplace is to get things done through employees. To do this the manager should be able to motivate employees. But that's easier said than done! Motivation practice and theory are difficult subjects, touching on several disciplines.

Motivation results from the interaction of both conscious and unconscious factors such as the intensity of desire or need, incentive or reward value of the goal, and expectations of the individual and of his or her peers. These factors are the reasons one has for behaving a certain way. An example is a student that spends extra time studying for a test because he or she wants a better grade in the class. Internal and external factors that stimulate desire and energy in people to be continually interested and committed to a job, role or subject, or to make an effort to attain a goal. Most employees need motivation to feel good about their jobs and perform optimally. Some employees are money motivated while others find recognition and rewards personally motivating.

Motivation levels within the workplace have a direct impact on employee productivity. Workers who are motivated and excited about their jobs carry out their responsibilities to the best of their ability and production numbers increase as a result. An incentive is a motivating influence that is designed to drive behavior and motivate employees to produce quality work. Employers use several types of incentives to increase production numbers. Employee incentives come in a variety of forms including paid time off, bonuses, cash and travel perks. Incentives drive employee motivation because they offer workers more to strive for than a regular paycheck. Many employees need recognition from their employers to produce quality work. Recognition and employee reward systems identify employees who perform their jobs well. Acknowledging a job well done makes employees feel good and encourages them to do good things. Employers recognize workers by tracking progress and providing feedback about how they have improved over time. Public recognition is also a motivating factor that drives worker productivity.

2. Review of Literature

Elizabeth Boye et al (2016) focussed on the risk factors associated with the mining industry, management has to ensure that employees are well motivated to curb the rate at which employees embark on industrial unrest which affect performance, and employees are to comply with health and safety rules because the industry contribute hugely to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country.

Hackman and Oldham (1980) urged that organizations have to restructure work to induce intrinsic motivation. Greater skill variety, task identity, and task significance increases the experienced meaningfulness of work, autonomy raises experienced responsibility, and feedback provides knowledge of results.

Hafiza et al. (2011) found that there are several factors that can affect employee performance like training and development opportunities, working conditions, worker-employer relationship, job security and company over all policies and procedures for rewarding employees. Among the factors that affect employee performance, motivation that comes with rewards is of utmost importance.

Ioan Moise Achim, Larisa Dragolea, George Balan (2013) said that the financial side of motivation is widely preferred and known by the both parts –employer and employee. In the present study we shall insist and plead for the possibilities of application and the results of the efficient non - financial motivation plan to the internal climate and the lasting performance of the firm.

Ismajli et al.(2015) identified that the factors that motivate employees as human resources in local government serve as a basis for increasing the service quality. He found that salary of workers, professional advancement and opportunity for promotion appear to be among the most important factors of motivation. The other important factors that the study revealed are work conditions, as well as the evaluation and the objective assessment of performance measurement.

Muogbo U.S (2013) found that there existed relationship between employee motivation and the organizational performance. The study reveals that extrinsic motivation given to workers in an organization has a significant influence on the workers performance.

Rajeswari Devadass (2011) worked on employee motivational practices & found that how job characteristics, employee characteristic, management practices and broader environmental factors influence employees' motivation. She confirms motivation concepts are central to employees. Job characteristics, management practices, employee characteristics and broader environmental factors are the key variables influence employees' motivation in organization.

Stephen A. Furlich (2016) addresses employees' expectations of performance rewards and their motivation by understanding communication with their managers through the use of Expectancy-Valence Theory. He focused on specific aspects of communication such as communication behaviors, expectations, communication interactions, and outcomes from the communication interactions. These areas of communication are also applied to general areas within the social sciences.

Vinay Chaitanya Ganta (2014) studied on Motivation levels within the workplace and found that it shows direct impact on employee productivity. Workers who are motivated and excited about their jobs carry out their responsibilities to the best of their ability and production numbers increases as a result. Employee motivation has always been a central problem for leaders and managers. Employers need to get to know their employees very well and use different tactics to motivate each of them based on their personal wants and needs.

3. Objectives of the Study

- To identify the factors that motivates employees.
- To study employee's opinion regarding job motivation factors.
- To suggest measures for improvement of motivational aspects in organization.

4. Research Methodology

Sample and Data

The location for the study is restricted to the Telecom industry located in Kadapa district of Andhra Pradesh. The criteria for selection of the respondents for the study were the employees of all categories working on permanent as well as contract basis. The total sample size was comprised of 120 employees, who were selected by stratified random sampling method.

Data collection was carried out with the prior permission of the Manager of that company and contacted the employees to get the responses. This data collection work is carried out during lunch time and completion of working hours. Good rapport with company employees was established by giving introduction about the objective of the study, importance of their co-operation and sincere responses before the distribution of the questionnaire. The employees were informed about the confidentiality of the information. They were given enough time to answer all the statements.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no relationship between Demographic factors and employee motivation.

Data Analysis

Factor Analysis

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.478
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	924.664
	Df	190
	Sig.	.000

The K.M.O value of 0.478 indicates that the condition is “good” for further tests to be carried out

SPSS has extracted 8 factors based on Kaiser’s criterion of retaining factors with eigenvalues

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
salary and wages	1.000	.732
Bonus	1.000	.766
medical reimbursements	1.000	.761
Insurances	1.000	.763
housing facilities	1.000	.805
retirement benefits	1.000	.810
setting work related goals	1.000	.730
good relationship with co workers	1.000	.670
work participation in management	1.000	.685
effective promotional activities	1.000	.760
safety measures	1.000	.823
organizational recognition	1.000	.768
Acknowledgement	1.000	.667
Leaves	1.000	.756
motivational taks	1.000	.600
work environment	1.000	.803
training methods	1.000	.766
Competition	1.000	.813
job security exists in the organization	1.000	.718
satisfied highly with motivational factors	1.000	.753
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

greater than 1.Kaiser’s criterion is accurate when there are less than 30 variables and the communalities after extraction are greater than 0.6. For these data, there are 8 variables and the mean communality is 0.74685 so extracting eight factors are warranted.

Component Matrix ^a								
	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
salary and wages	.660	-.037	.006	-.327	-.228	.200	-.138	.277
Bonus	-.538	-.504	.396	.006	-.247	.048	-.015	-.047
medical reimbursements	-.261	.036	.641	.423	-.269	-.152	-.080	-.010
Insurances	-.093	-.184	.343	-.304	.318	-.128	.623	.071
housing facilities	-.451	.175	-.608	.223	.310	-.175	.030	.154
retirement benefits	-.595	-.014	.117	-.210	.421	.264	.036	-.387
medical reimbursements	.001	.389	-.218	.422	-.252	-.074	.112	-.521
good relationship with co workers	.464	.574	.010	.024	.227	.158	.201	-.094
work participation in management	.243	.582	.269	-.430	.099	-.129	.041	.023
effective promotional activities	-.365	.217	.413	-.048	.280	-.246	-.256	.450
safety measures	.447	-.426	-.470	.151	.012	-.388	.026	.215
organizational recognition	-.090	.747	-.044	-.165	-.310	-.048	.183	.203
Acknowledgement	-.608	-.028	-.398	-.135	-.091	.089	.321	.006
Leaves	.378	-.488	-.105	-.146	-.056	-.544	.134	-.161
motivational tasks	.148	.497	.062	.527	-.006	-.142	.037	.126
work environment	.364	-.181	-.089	.338	.111	.371	.547	.258
training methods	-.402	-.035	-.508	-.090	-.080	.434	-.305	.218
Competition	.291	-.247	.298	.526	.456	.267	-.122	.086
job security exists in the organization	.466	.110	-.185	-.142	.456	-.131	-.369	-.269
satisfied highly with motivational factors	.711	-.124	.149	-.114	-.202	.368	-.017	-.142
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.								

8 factors have been extracted, based on the criterion that only factors with eigenvalues of 1 or more should be extracted. Cumulative percentage of variance explained column extracted 8 factors together account for 74.6% of the total variance.

Component 1 leads to: Satisfied highly with motivational factors (711)

Component 2 leads to: Organization recognition (747)

Component 3 leads to: Medical reimbursements (641)

Component 4 leads to: Motivation tasks (527)

Component 5 leads to: Retirement benefits (421)

Component 6 leads to: Training methods (434)

Component 7 leads to: Insurances (623)

Component 8 leads to: Effective promotional activities (450)

Interpretation

By this factor analysis, it is clear that the above 8 components have maximum importance to increases the satisfaction level of BSNL employees. Therefore, the above three factor/component have significant effect in the satisfaction level of employees and each of the factor related to safety at work place is inversely proportional to the satisfaction level. So, emphasizing on the above factor leads to improvement in the satisfaction level of employees.

CHI-SQUARE TEST

s.no	Factors	p-value	Df	Chi-square
1	Gender			
	1.1 Insurances	12.373	3	0.005
	1.2 Motivational Tasks	20.567	3	0.000
	1.3 Leaves	13.606	3	0.003
	1.4 Good Relationship With Co-Workers	22.188	3	0.000
	1.5 Retirement Benefits	23.678	9	0.005
	1.6 Setting Work Related Goals	26.564	3	0.000
2	Age (In Years)			
	2.1 Salary And Wages	14.222 ^a	3	.003
	2.2 Bonus	57.930 ^a	9	.000
	2.3 Medical Reimbursements	30.508 ^a	6	.000
	2.4 Setting Work Related Goals	26.564 ^a	3	.000
	2.5 Good Relationship With Co Workers	22.188 ^a	3	.000
	2.6 Effective Promotional Activities	17.233 ^a	3	.001
	2.7 Leaves	13.606 ^a	3	.003
	2.8 Motivational Tasks	20.567 ^a	3	.000
3	Marital Status			
	3.1 Salary And Wages	29.189 ^a	1	.000
	3.2 Bonus	17.383 ^a	3	.001
	3.3 Good Relationship With Co Workers	22.426 ^a	3	.000
	3.4 Work Participation In Management	21.502 ^a	3	.000
	3.5 Effective Promotional Activities	26.306 ^a	3	.000
	3.6 Satisfied Highly With Motivational Factors	14.387 ^a	2	.001
4	Employee status			
	4.1 Retirement Benefits	38.750 ^a	3	.000
	4.2 Setting Work Related Goals	16.667 ^a	3	.001
	4.3 Safety Measures	14.792 ^a	3	.002
	4.4 Acknowledgement	30.714 ^a	3	.000
	4.5 Motivational Tasks	28.188 ^a	3	.000
	4.6 Work Environment	14.068 ^a	2	.001
	4.7 Competition	13.542 ^a	3	.004
	4.8 Satisfied Highly Motivational Tasks	14.006 ^a	2	.001
5	Work experience			
	5.1 Retirement Benefits	48.878 ^a	9	.000
	5.2 Good Relationship With Co-Workers	40.397 ^a	9	.000
	5.3 Effective Promotional Activities	40.993 ^a	9	.000
	5.4 Safety Measures	56.382 ^a	9	.000
	5.5 Organizational Recognition	57.434 ^a	9	.000
	5.6 Job Security	19.159 ^a	6	.004
6	Designation			
	6.1 Salary And Wages	18.400 ^a	3	.000
	6.2 Bonus	26.222 ^a	9	.002

6.3 Medical Reimbursements	27.250 ^a	6	.000
6.4 Insurances	27.355 ^a	9	.001
6.5 Housing Facilities	25.792 ^a	9	.002
6.6 Retirement Benefits	29.117 ^a	9	.001
6. Setting Work Related Goals	47.900 ^a	9	.000
6.8 Effective Promotional Activities	28.970 ^a	9	.001
6.9 Organizational Recognition	68.762 ^a	9	.000
6.10 Work Environment	22.984 ^a	6	.001
6.11 Training Methods	20.400 ^a	6	.002
6.12 Good Relationship With Co-Workers	28.970 ^a	9	.001

Interpretation

The above table reveals that p value is less than 0.05. Therefore null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore we can say that there is no association between demographic factors and the various aspects related to employee motivation. It reveals that irrespective of age, gender, marital status, employee status, work experience and designation the employee motivation is same.

5. Suggestions

- Employee empowerment may be provided to employees in achieving high employee satisfaction and motivation.
- Effective promotional activities may be provided to improve employee morale, achieving the desired unity and concern for employee well being with reduction in HR cost.
- Acknowledgement may be provided to employees that refer to the process of identifying and accomplishing the employee's career objective through systematic way of skill identification assessment and development.
- Company need to concentrate on providing motivational things to the employees irrespective of their age, gender, designation, employment status, marital status and work experience as it creates more dedication and support from the employees to the management.

6. Conclusion

From the above study it is concluded that motivation is achieved through both extrinsic and intrinsic motivators. Without such motivators employees do not concentrate on the performance when they are at the work place. Therefore, management should concentrate on providing better motivators in order to enhance productivity of the organization as well as to increase the profitability of the company which ultimately leads to better economic development of the country directly or indirectly.

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